

Women Empowerment Through Milk Production Cooperative Societies: An Economic Analysis

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ABSTRACT:

The present study based on an empirical survey of women members of milk production cooperation societies in Vijayapur district, by taking into consideration of the socio-economic variables like age-group, educational status, caste affiliations and economic status like family profession income and ownership of assets etc. In this concern the study aims to evolution of those involving in milk production cooperative societies in vijayapur district, its indicated that growth in milk production cooperative societies have increased significantly in the past 3 decades and there were 14 milk production unions are working covering all the districts in the year of 2020, the state with 14682 Dairy Cooperatives functioning and 25.30 lakh milk producers. The impact of cooperative societies on women respondents has been studied in relation to income employment generation, economic independence and social empowerment in terms of family decision making and participation in social and political activities. Hence the present research problem is stated as "Women Empowerment through Milk Production Societies: An Economic Analysis"

The milk production cooperatives societies in India have been formed to improve the socio-economic and political conditions of women empowerment especially in the weaker sections societies. The milk production cooperative societies are also one of the essential for rural and semi-rural poor's, which helps to improvement of socio-economic activities, reduction of poverty, opportunity to income and employment generation, sustainable livelihood to millions of women's household in rural-semi urban in Vijayapur district as well as Karnataka. It is found that Milk Production Cooperative Societies has positive impact on the women empowerment through developing cooperatives societies. There is much more strengthening of cooperative societies in order to overall development and the women community in the society.

KEYWORDS:

Milk Production, Cooperative, Urban, Opportunity

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Introduction:

The women empowerment is one of the major challenging tasks in the present scenario. Majority of women residence in both rural and urban area, are employed in order to meet the socio-economic conditions and financial demands for sustainable development, most of them are engaged in agriculture activities, animal husbandry, cattle rearing, poultry rearing, piggery rearing, dairy farming, fisheries activities and also other subsidiary activities such as the dairy cooperatives societies. The milk production cooperative societies are provides opportunities of employment, income generation, improvement of socio-economic activities, reduction of poverty, sustainable livelihood to millions of women's household in rural and semi-urban area. In this direction, present study is an effort to study the impact of Women Milk Production Co-operative Societies on women's empowerment. It can be proved that so, women participation in business activities and day-today affairs of dairy co-operatives are an essential factor for the improvement in the socio-economic conditions of the women. In this concern the study aims to evolution especially those involving women in milk production cooperative societies in Vijayapur district, its indicated that growth of milk production societies have increased significantly in the past 3 decades and there were 14 milk unions are working covering all the districts in the year of 2020, the state with 14682 Dairy Cooperatives functioning covers 25.30 lakh milk producers. The impact of cooperative societies on women respondents has been studied in relation to income employment generation, economic independence and social empowerment in terms of family decision making and participation in social and political activities. Hence the present research problem is stated as; "Women Empowerment through Milk Production Cooperative Societies: An Economic Analysis"

Objectives:

1. To analyze livelihood strategies of members belonged to milk production cooperative societies in the study area
2. To explore the milk production cooperative societies on income generation and changes in socio-economic status of respondents.
3. To suggest policy measures to ensure sustainable women's empowerment

Methodology:

Keeping these observations in the background, the study discusses methodology adopted in conducting the study. The present study is based on secondary sources information, the secondary sources was collected from the office records of the Milk Federation, Milk Unions and Department of Registrar of Cooperative, Government of Karnataka and the primary data is collected through the structured interview schedules administered to the sample households exclusively selected for the presented study. The statistical tools like Mean and Percentages are used to analysis and interpretation of the data.

The study intensive to covers five milk production cooperative societies in different talukas of vijayapur district where the concentration of women is very high. The study covered a total 100 respondent women members of the cooperative societies. The 20 women respondents from each cooperative society were selected on random sample basis such as Kadlewad Milk Cooperative Society, Kaggod Milk Cooperative Society, Kallakavatagi Milk Cooperative Society, Kalagi Milk Cooperative Society and Kalagi Milk Cooperative Society in vijayapur district.

Distribution of Sample Households by Social Groups:

Social and economic backwardness of the different social groups and the demographic factor in the study areas seems to have influenced the milk production cooperative societies for promoting savings and entrepreneurship among the different social groups. The sample households by social groups are presented in following Table No.1.

Table No-1: Category wise distribution of Women Respondents by Social Groups

Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage
SC	17	17.00
ST	13	13.00
OBC	38	38.00
Minority	05	05.00
GM	27	27.00
Total	100	100.00

Source: Primary Data

Significant trends are observed relating to the distribution of women sample households by social groups in the study area. Majority of 38.00 percent of women belonged to other back ward class followed by 27.00 percent come under general merit less percent i.e., 05.00 percent members were relatively few compared to those belonging to other social groups.

Distribution of Respondents by Age groups:

It is an established fact that age plays a dominant role in shaping a personality of an individual. The age factor is inter-related with the ability to learn, group and retain. Level of participation in different walks of life and holding of several responsibilities are determined to a great extent by age. The stages of life cycle of women are especially affected by the age. The age-wise distribution of respondents has been obtained to understand their qualitative and quantitative contributions to their groups. The Table No. 2 reflects details.

Table No-2: Category wise distribution of respondents by Age groups

Social Groups	Upto 30	31 - 40	41 - 50	51 above	Total
SC	00	35.29	58.83	5.88	100(17)
ST	00	38.47	46.16	15.38	100(13)
OBC	2.77	30.56	44.45	22.22	100(36)
Minority	00	40.00	60.00	00	100(05)
GM	7.40	29.63	33.34	29.63	100(27)
Total	03	32	44	19	100(100)

Source: Primary Data

The data obtained from the respondent of milk production cooperative societies, about the age groups of members have indicated that majority of members of all categories women's belonged to the age group of 41-51 years. This trend is found among the members of MPCs belonging to different social groups' viz., SC, ST, OBC, Minority and GM social groups in Milk Production Cooperative Societies followed by in the age group of 31-40 years constituted a substantial percentage of the total members and remaining others two groups accounted very less respondents belonging to societies. These age groups represent economically

active participants in societies Groups with necessary zeal and experience. The percentage of young respondents up to 30 years and of those in the advanced age groups is small varying between 2.77 percentages and 7.40 percentage of the total.

Educational Status of Respondents by Social Groups:

Education is again one such important factors which affects the attitudes and shapes the personality of individuals in a positive manner. Besides, enhancing information and awareness level, education is an important ingredient for social and economic development. The members have little access to education due to social, economic, cultural and situational reasons. The mental abilities improved through formal education might lead to qualitative involvement in the societies, income generation and banking functions. Details can be seen from Table No. 03

Table No-3: Educational Status of Respondents by Social Group

Category	Illiteracy	Primary	High School	Pre-University	Total
SC	5.88	88.24	11.77	00.00	100(17)
ST	7.70	76.93	23.07	00.00	100(13)
OBC	7.89	63.16	26.32	00.00	100(38)
Minority	20.00	60.00	00.00	20.00	100(05)
GM	00.00	66.67	22.23	3.70	100(27)
Total	06	71	21	02	100(100)

Source: Primary Data

Educational status has a direct impact on an individual's level of understanding management and organizational ability etc. Hence the educational status plays an important role in all these aspects relating to the members. The study has revealed that majority of household members had Middle school and High school level of education followed by those who had pre-primary/primary education. A relatively lesser number of household members had pre-university level education. Those with degree, post graduate, technical/professional education constituted a negligible of the total.

Distribution of Respondents by Occupation:

The family occupation of the individuals decides the economic condition as well as the social status. The main occupation profile of the

respondents is exhibits in the following Table No.4

Table No-4: Distribution of Respondents by Occupation and Social Groups

Category	Agriculture	Agriculture Labour	Non-Agri. labour	Self Employed	Total
SC	82.36	5.89	11.76	00.00	100(17)
ST	84.62	7.70	7.70	00.00	100(13)
OBC	78.95	10.53	7.89	2.63	100(38)
Minority	60.00	00.00	20.00	20.00	100(05)
GM	96.30	00.00	00.00	3.70	100(27)
Total	84	06	07	03	100(100)

Source: Primary Data

It is significant to find out data obtained from the respondents of Milk Production Cooperative Societies covered by the study that majority of 84 respondents of them were agricultural background for their livelihood. This trend is largely similar among all the respondents belonging to different social groups like SC, ST, and OBC followed by 7.89 percent to 20.00 percent of the respondents were involved in no-agricultural labour, while 60.00 percent to 96.30 percent were engaged mainly in agriculture. However there is a wide variation of number of respondents belonging to different social groups whose main occupation was agriculture. It is found that only 2.63 percent to 20.00 percent of respondent members of societies were self employed. The occupational status of the social groups covered by the study indicates that the income level of the respondents is low and they are economically weak.

Monthly Average Savings

The particulars monthly average savings of respondents are given in Table No. 5

Table No-5: Category wise Monthly Savings of respondents

Cate- gory	Before					After				
	1000	2000	3000	4000	Total	2000	3000	4000	5000	Total
SC	52.95	35.30	11.76	00.00	100(17)	5.89	17.65	29.41	47.05	100(17)
ST	53.85	38.47	7.69	00.00	100(13)	7.69	15.39	7.69	69.24	100(13)

Mi- nority	60.00	40.00	00.00	00.00	100(05)	00.00	40.00	40.00	20.00	100(05)
OBC	52.64	31.58	10.52	5.26	100(38)	00.00	18.43	26.32	55.26	100(38)
GM	48.15	29.63	14.81	7.40	100(27)	7.40	7.40	29.63	15.56	100(27)
Total	52	33	11	4	100(100)	4	16	26	54	100(100)

Source: Primary Data

The impact of Milk Production Cooperative Societies on respondents is reflected in generating average monthly saving at various institutional levels. The study has revealed that the number of respondents who started savings with the various institutional level has gone up after they joined to milk production cooperative societies. The increasing percentage of respondents in maintaining cumulative savings indicate the increasing savings capacity due to joining to societies. Thus there is a trend of a substantial increase in the total average monthly savings of respondents after the milk production.

Conclusion:

Women empowerment is a multi dimensional process, which will become a reality through a combined effort of various factors that contribute to it among them the milk production cooperative societies also one. The milk production cooperatives societies in India have been formed to improve the socio-economic conditions, empowerment of economically, socially and politically of women milk producers, especially the weaker sections of the societies. The milk production cooperative societies are one of the essential for rural and semi-rural poor women milk producers in study area. It is helps to improvement of socio-economic activities, reduction of poverty, opportunity of income and employment generation, sustainable livelihood to millions of women's household in rural-semi urban in Vijayapur district. It is found that Milk Production Cooperative Societies has positive impact on the women empowerment through developing cooperatives societies in the area. There is much more strengthening of cooperative societies in order to overall development and the women community in the society.

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Conflict of interest:

The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

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